

The Application of E-Pbb Public Service Innovations in the Lamongan Revenue Service Department and the Obstacle Factors

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Abstract

Innovation in the government agencies is needed in the process of providing public services by developing new methods and new resources. In addition, innovations in the public sector can be implemented in order to increase the effectiveness and efficiency of public services. However, in the implementing public service innovations, there are obstacles.

In this study, the sampling technique is purposive sampling. The analysis technique used in this study is using interactive model analysis. According to Miles, Huberman and Saldana.

The results of the research are obstacle factors such as human resources, employee mutations that make the e-PBB public service innovation program not run properly and internet connections are limited, there are some areas or villages that still lack internet signal which can be said that the e-PBB program does not work properly well.

Key word : *Innovation, the obstacle factor for innovation*

INTRODUCTION

Public service innovation is a new breakthrough to provide benefits to society. Innovation is a new tool, thing, or idea where it has never existed before, where the creation of this new thing is expected to be something interesting and useful.

Innovation in government institutions are needed in the process of providing public services by developing new methods and new resources. In addition, innovation in the public sector can be implemented in order to increase efficiency and reduce costs considering that basically public sector organizations are always faced with scarcity of resources and budget constraints. The government in innovating to take advantage of technological advances, it is hoped that the government can provide services to the society. Innovative public services require conducive conditions both in terms of service unit managers and from the side of ministerial or institutional also local government leadership that allow creativity to grow and develop. The concept of innovation in Indonesia is increasing developing along with developments over time, especially technological developments because the dynamics of change are marked by the development of technological advances and knowledge, so human resources are required to play an active role, the current trend of success in every country due to innovation factor. Innovation has several impacts on the condition of organizations and agencies, especially Government. To maintain an organization in the environment requires innovation. Because innovation can bring better organization and can be effective and efficient in achieving organizational goals and targets, by innovation it is expected to be able to become solutions that occur due to changes and environmental complexity.

Reminding that society can be more critically to get the best service from the government. The society is free to compare government bureaucratic services with other public services. Therefore, every service must be sought to find a solution so it can be done immediately. Increasing the effectiveness of the performance of the apparatus needs attention, accompanied by a commitment, always create and innovate. Several cities have implemented innovations by utilizing technology, one of which is Lamongan city which has implemented the e-PBB public service innovation service.

The application of e-PBB public service innovation is inseparable from obstacles. The application of innovation cannot be separated from constraints in the field, human resources and limited internet connections. The obstacle factor in e-PBB public service innovation is the human resource factor, that is not ready in number but also in quality.

HR is an important factor for institutions because almost all operational activities of the institution are carried out by humans. Achievement of institutional goals is determined by the quality of its human resources, but in the government many employees are placed not in accordance with their fields, this can also hinder the achievement of institutional goals. Furthermore, an uncomfortable work environment will make employees unproductive and innovative.

LITERATURE REVIEW

A. The Obstacle Factors for Innovation

Innovation in the public sector is very synonymous and is often associated with changes or reforms carried out by the government which is better known as the concept of new public management (NPM). To get good innovation, the government must pay attention to the innovation process first because by paying attention to the innovation process, the government will be able to see and predict the failure and success of an innovation, in seeing the failure and success of an innovation, first look at the process, application and supporting factors. and the inhibitor after it is evaluated it will be able to see the innovation can be said to be successful or not.

Innovation does not occur smoothly or without obstacles. Many of the cases of innovation are constrained by various factors. Usually organizational culture is the biggest inhibiting factor in promoting an innovation. Apart from organizational culture factors, there are many factors that can hinder the growth of innovation in an organization. According to Albury, the inhibiting factors for innovation in the public sector include:

Picture 1.1 Barriers to Innovation
Source: Mulgan Albury, 2003. p.31

- a) *Reluctance to close down failing program or organization.* That is, a program or even an organizational unit that clearly shows failure will be better closed and replaced with a new program or unit that is more promising. Failure is commonplace in innovation, but reluctance to stop failure means closing opportunities for better change. In the private sector, closing a failed business or stopping a project that is losing money is commonplace, but in the public sector it tends to be more difficult to do this, even though it's not impossible.
- b) *Over-reliance on high performers as source of innovation.* So far, there is a tendency that change or innovation is only possible if there is a strong figure who has high consistency. Once that figure is gone, all reform initiatives will disappear. That is why, innovative ideas must be institutionalized so that they do not depend on one's personality and can be guaranteed their sustainability.
- c) *Technologies available but constraining cultural or organizational arrangements.* Often innovation fails not because of the absence of technology support, but rather because of organizational traditions or policies that are not pro-innovation. The perception that differences in ideas are a form of disobedience to leadership, for example, is an example of a cultural problem that is often encountered in an organization. Likewise, the absence of a system of incentives for a reformer, or the obligation to get approval for an innovation initiative, is an example of a policy that is neither pro-innovation nor friendly.
- d) *No rewards or incentives to innovate or adopt innovations.* Appreciation in order to foster employee motivation to give the best for the institution is only natural. So, innovation and appreciation are

actually two inseparable sides. The ability to innovate cannot be considered as a matter of mediocrity or normal performance, but must be seen as something special so that it deserves appreciation.

- e) *Poor skills in active risk or change management.* However, the skill aspect plays a role in the success of innovation. No matter how big the motivation of employees and a conducive environment but not supported by adequate skills, innovation will still stop as a discourse.
- f) *Short-term budget and planning horizons.* Budget support is a necessity for innovation. The experience of many developed countries that budget research and innovation funds of up to 3% and GDP has provided evidence that economic progress based on innovation and technology is the result of long-term investment. For this reason, the development of innovation both on an organizational and national scale must be well planned not only from an annual perspective, but also from a medium and long term perspective.
- g) *Delivery pressures and administrative burdens.* In ex-colonial countries, administrative aspects often become obstacles in the management of certain functions, including innovation. The relationship between the state and society or between leaders and employees is often based on distrust. Consequently, for a small business only (eg licensing services) must include many requirements, long procedures, and involve multiple actors. Things like this put pressure on anyone with an interest and eliminate the desire to innovate.
- h) *Culture of risk aversion.* Failure to bear the impact of a choice is a psychological as well as a cultural obstacle to progress. Risk is seen as something that must be avoided and even shunned, not something that actually provides a new, more energetic challenge that must be faced.

In public service, there is pressure not only to develop innovations but also to share with other organizations in order to increase public value. Transfer of learning is an interactive process of knowledge creation and transfer between managers and policy makers, not passive copying of best practice.

In addition, to stay competitive in today's economic development, organizations must be innovative. However, sometimes organizations fail to innovate because they are influenced by 3 factors, such as:

- a. Lack of resources. Lack of resources in a company or organization causes that organization to be unable to innovate, both limited human resources and limited natural resources. Limited capital also often makes innovation programs or does not employ what is necessary to become an innovator.
- b. Failure to recognize opportunities. Inability to absorb all innovations, companies need to develop the ability to evaluate carefully to select the one that has the greatest potential. To gain a competitive advantage. An organization must make investment decisions before the innovation process reaches a mature stage. If the organization is not skilled in recognizing and evaluating the opportunities that exist, a company should not be too careful because it can cause failure to invest in innovations that will be a success for other companies.
- c. Rejection of change. Most organizations tend to resist a change, whereas innovation means being able to afford old products and old ways of doing things and replacing them in new products and new ways of doing things. This type of change is difficult for managers and organizational members and slows down the innovation process.

RESEARCH METHOD

In line with the problems and objectives of the study, the researchers used a qualitative research approach with the type of descriptive research. The type of data collected in this study can be divided into two namely secondary data and primary data. Source of data in this study focuses on human sources, events and documentation. In this study the sampling technique used was purposive sampling. The main data collection techniques in this study are interviews, observation and documentation. The analysis technique used in this study is to use interactive model analysis. According to Miles, Huberman and Saldana (2014: 14).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. The Obstacle factors of the e-PBB public service innovation process in the Lamongan Revenue Service Department

From time to time, the concept of innovation will continue to develop. Organizations cannot be separated from the development of innovation in order to maintain the organization. Likewise, many

changes in service are one of the impacts of the existence of innovation and governmental organizations to innovate is an encouragement from society that increasingly demands good service, not only that with innovation it also brings better government organizations.

Innovation has a lot of impact on organizational conditions and the creativity in which innovation originates. The dynamics of rapid environmental changes marked by advances in science and technology require quality human resources, but behind that there are several inhibiting factors in the application of innovation.

The results of the research show that the obstacle factors in the application of e-PBB public service innovation in the Lamongan Revenue Service Department are as follows:

1) Limited Human Resources

One aspect that is no less important in an institution or agency is the human resources (HR) it has. Employees who are the driving force for mobility activities in an institution or service need to be managed professionally (Kasmir, 2011: 154).

In previous research by Alvydas Raipa & Vidmante Giedraityte, 2014: Innovation Process Barriers in Public Sector: A Comparative Analysis in Lithuania and the European Union, Calling innovation design and implementation one of the important conditions for modernizing society and government, however, the public sector innovation process is risky and success is not always guaranteed, so it is important to identify and prevent innovation barriers. Public sector organizations have the ability to identify innovation barriers and to develop their management instruments, determining the quality and efficiency of the innovation process. The most frequently cited barriers to public sector innovation are lack of inception and human resources, lack of management support and quality human resources, risk-averse culture and employee resilience.

Managing employees as one of the most important assets for an institution or agency starts from determining the positions required by the agency or how many positions will be required. Then, determining the duties, principal, functions, authorities and responsibilities of each position. To enter a position requires certain skills because not all master IT.

Employee mutation is one of the policies of regional leaders, because indeed employee mutations have been regulated in the Government Regulation No. 41 Year of 2007 concerning Regional Apparatus Organizations. Unequal human resources in each village can affect the management of a website. Although it can be learned, understanding to the world of technology that is still lacking makes village websites less attractive. Even if there are capable human resources, the limited time and energy of website managers also becomes an obstacle to the existence of the web. Not all agencies have capable human resources. There is a solution where you can accept website material contributions from anywhere, but it is not yet fully implemented in all Dinas. Likewise, as from the findings in the field, it is known that there are employee mutations that make the e-PBB public service innovation program not run properly, because not all can run an application or the web, so it can be observed from the results of interviews in the previous chapter not only employee mutations make a lack of human resources and can be an obstacle but also a lack of quality of human resources in the e-PBB service innovation team because employees only receive training for 3 (three) months there is no further training, this has resulted in a lack of staff numbers and also low quality of human resources by the Lamongan Revenue Service Department. This is in accordance with the theory of inhibiting factors according to Watson, 1999. Albury, 2003. That one of the inhibiting factors is excessive dependence on high performance.

The employee transfer policy is a policy that is quite normative because this transfer policy is absolutely necessary, even if a regional government does not make a transfer, it can be interpreted that something is not good. The purpose of the job transfer itself is to make changes in the organization and is expected to be able to make these transferred employees more developed, an increase in employee productivity, employee career development and additional work units needed.

The results of the research show that there is rejection of innovation due to limited human resources which hinders innovation, namely rejection from certain groups such as traditional communities who are already comfortable with the old way.

Good quality and advanced human resources will have a positive effect on the agency itself. For example, in an organization many HR consists of employees. In order for the organization to develop and progress, competent and quality human resources are needed to support the progress of the organization to

make that HR quality. HR needs to be trained and upgraded because HR is an asset that is valuable for a company to develop and compete with its competitors. Broadly speaking, training is a process that educates and trains employees in terms of skills and attitudes to be able to carry out job responsibilities properly.

2) Limited Internet Connection

Apart from the human resource factor, the thing that is closely related to website management and information disclosure is an internet connection. Today, the use of the internet is no longer considered taboo, from villages to cities, many people use the internet, its development is so fast and very fast.

Internet users around the world are experiencing very rapid development, including in Indonesia. But this is not in line with the facilities and infrastructure in the village. From the research findings, it is known that there are some areas that are not covered by an internet connection. If it is affordable, the signal is very minimal so that this results in not supporting the e-PBB public service innovation program.

Here are the areas where the signal is still difficult:

Table 1.1 Village with Low Signal

NO	Village Name	Access Power
1	Jatipandak village, Sambeng district	Less than 1 Mbps
2	Sukomalo village, Kedungpring district	Less than 1 Mbps
3	Pamotan village, Sambeng district	Less than 1 Mbps
4	Sawen village, Sambeng district	Less than 1 Mbps
5	Cancing village, Sambeng district	Less than 1 Mbps
6	Randu Mbener village, Kembangbahu district	Less than 1 Mbps
7	Pucangro village, Sukodadi district	Less than 1 Mbps
8	Latukan village, Karanggeneng district	Less than 1 Mbps
9	Maor village, Kembangbahu district	Less than 1 Mbps
10	Rungkut village, Mantup district	Less than 1 Mbps

Source: self-managed in 2019

From that data above, it can be said that there are some areas or villages that still have minimal internet signal, which can be said that the e-PBB program is not running well. So infrastructure improvements are needed because with good infrastructure, not only e-PBB public services are running well but also other public services are also running well, it is very necessary to improve. This is one of the stages in an innovation process, namely minimizing an obstacle. So it can be said that there are some areas or villages that still have minimal internet signal, which can be said that the e-PBB program is not running well. So infrastructure improvements are needed because with good infrastructure, not only e-PBB public services are running well but also other public services are also running well, it is very necessary to improve. This is one of the stages in an innovation process, namely minimizing an obstacle.

The mapping of this area is because there are several areas that are difficult to reach by the internet network, which are in remote villages. These remote areas need special handling. Since 2003, Lamongan has announced that it will take advantage of technological advances in community services, marked in the building of an electronic data office (PDE). This is an effort made by the Lamongan government to provide information to the public with online media. However, the Lamongan government still has to prepare several things in the e-PBB process, one of which is to prepare a village that is indeed very remote and not connected to the internet.

The discovery of several areas with minimal signal, then the next process is to find problems then make adjustments or equalization with the innovations that will be implemented. This stage ensures that the innovation is feasible to be applied in the organization. The hope of matching before implementation is to know the possibilities faced in implementation, estimate the risks faced.

CONCLUSION

The application of e-PBB public service innovations is inseparable from obstacles, there are human resources and limited internet connections. One of the obstacle factors for innovation is the existence of

employee mutations which prevent the e-PBB public service innovation program from running properly, because not all can run an application or the web, so it can be observed from the results of interviews in the previous chapter that it is not only employee mutations that indicate a lack of Human resources and there are some areas or villages which still lack internet signal, that can be said if the e-PBB program is not running well. So, infrastructure improvements are needed, because with good infrastructure, not only e-PBB public services are running well but also other public services will get the impact of it, it is very necessary to improve.

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